

A MODEL OF FORMING LIBRARY CULTURE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article studies the pedagogical and psychological features and an effective model of forming a reading culture in older preschool children. The author discusses the mechanisms for arousing children's interest in books, systematically developing reading skills, and establishing cooperation between the family and the preschool educational organization. The model proposed in the article also serves to increase children's speech, aesthetic taste, and independent thinking. The article is intended for specialists in the field of preschool education, educators, and parents.*

Keywords: *preschool educational organization, speech, reading, thinking, intellect, educator, pupil, mechanism, creativity, ability.*

Creating a favorable emotional environment in the educational process is one of the important pedagogical factors in shaping a child's positive attitude towards reading. The use of digital educational resources in preschool educational organizations arouses great interest in children and encourages them to actively participate. The digital educational environment is convenient for the child, rich in interactive and motivational opportunities, and also creates ample conditions for implementing an individual approach. Through such tools, it is possible to form a reading culture in children, model various problem situations, and carry out activities that are difficult to organize in typical group classes. For example, a student performs situational exercises such as going to a virtual store to buy clothes, walking with a friend to the zoo, explaining his condition to a doctor, or retelling the content of a fairy tale to a teacher. As a result of the use of digital resources, the possibilities of working with visual aids, pictures, photos, videos, historical archive materials, electronic and printed books are significantly expanded, and their educational effectiveness increases.

The concise and systematic presentation of educational material, the logical connection of new concepts with previously learned knowledge, helps the child to perceive the subject holistically. In addition, the ability to change the size of the object on the screen, to repeatedly review certain parts of it, develops concentration and observation in children. The integrative function of electronic learning tools is also important for preschoolers. In such tools, educational material is presented in small, logically completed parts. At the same time, various didactic methods are used to attract the child's attention and keep him active. The child has the opportunity to independently choose the topic, the form in which he will receive information, determine its level of complexity, the type of task and the method of its implementation. As a result, he becomes an active subject of the educational process and organizes educational activities in accordance with his needs and interests.

In digital educational tools, the function of providing timely assistance in mastering educational material also plays an important role. This assistance is carried out through individual recommendations, explanations, guidelines and additional comments. Such assistance can be provided at the request of the student or automatically. For example, a child's prolonged

difficulty in completing a task, a series of incorrect completions of simple tasks, or a slow start to the activity indicate that he needs additional support. The form of assistance can range from brief advice to a step-by-step explanation of the task. At the same time, from a pedagogical point of view, it is important not to limit the child's independent activity, but to encourage him to complete more complex tasks within his existing capabilities.

The implementation of these functions is inextricably linked with such functions as educational, adaptive, integrative, corrective and timely assistance. At the same time, special attention should be paid to the compensatory function. This function involves assessing the child's results not by comparing them with other children, but rather by assessing the dynamics of development achieved in relation to his previous state. In this regard, the "surplus value" or individual growth indicator becomes an important criterion for pedagogical monitoring. Unlike control and diagnostics, monitoring involves systematic observation of the child's educational activities over a long period of time. This allows predicting future development results and making appropriate pedagogical decisions. In a digital educational environment, the control process is carried out continuously and is organized in an integrated manner with teaching. In this case, all the child's actions are recorded, and information about his difficulties and successes is collected. The diagnostic function of digital educational tools allows the educator to assess the child's activity, identify the causes of errors and determine in which direction additional assistance is needed. Pedagogical potential is manifested as a set of capabilities that are capable of directly or indirectly influencing the development of the individual, with or without the help of additional created conditions. Researchers emphasize such important features of pedagogical potential as competence, functionality, dynamism, connectivity and feasibility.

As part of our research (2022–2025), the model for forming a reading culture in preschool children based on an individual approach in preschool educational organizations was improved. This model made it possible to effectively test the system of tasks developed based on the author's program in the pilot testing process. As a result of the research, the model for forming a reading culture in preschool children was further enriched and improved.

The model incorporates the following main components:

1. Specific goal orientation. This component includes general goals aimed at forming a high level of reading culture in preschool children through familiarization with books, as well as specific goals such as developing emotional sensitivity, deep perception of the content of the book, and the formation of moral norms and values through reading. It also reflects aspects of the child's personal development based on the interrelationship of motivational, process and reflexive components.

2. Selection of the content of the activity. Within the framework of this component, two main, closely related directions were identified: a) the formation of a reading culture in children through the development of creativity, the development of emotional sensitivity and the enrichment of aesthetic perception; b) the organization of a system of tasks aimed at evaluating the activities of the heroes of fairy tales and works of art, adhering to moral standards and forming children's personal relationships.

3. The component of organizing the pedagogical process highlights the forms, methods and means of organizing collaborative activities that serve to achieve the set goal. Within the framework of this component, expressive storytelling of read fiction and fairy tales was chosen as the main organizational form. This type of activity is an effective pedagogical tool due to its inextricable connection with the principles of demonstrativeness and solidity, which are

considered important for older preschool children. The main methods are educational methods - analysis of books, composing stories, a demonstrative approach, creating a problem situation and improvisation; teaching methods - visual, verbal and problem-based research methods; motivational, cognitive, creative, meaningful and criterion-based methods aimed at attracting children to reading books were also identified. Fairy tales, examples of fiction, stories and fables, collections of riddles and proverbs were used as tools. The complementarity of these tools also expands the possibilities of creating audio and video materials.

4. The resulting component of the educational model reflected the levels of formation of reading culture in older preschool children and the criteria for their determination.

The process of teaching children to think orally based on works of fiction is inextricably linked with the activity of introducing them to literature and is an integral part of work aimed at understanding the content of the work and understanding the actions of the characters. In the process of forming a reading culture in children, it is important to plan the effectiveness of work in each group in advance. This creates favorable conditions for group discussion and joint task solving. Another effective way to form a reading culture in children is to tell a story based on a plan given in the form of questions or instructions. The plan helps the child to focus on the topic of the story, to consistently describe events, and to maintain meaningful connections. The educator outlines the main stages of the storytelling process. Instructions, in turn, prevent the child from forgetting the sequence of events and have a positive effect on expressing thoughts in detail, clearly and expressively. Creating a collective story is also an effective method. In this case, children come together to complete a common task. The educator draws up a story plan, identifies micro-topics and distributes them among the children. Each child independently develops his own part of the story. At first, the educator begins the story, and then the children continue it in turn. Such stories are created on the basis of children's previous experiences - excursions to school, acquaintance with school supplies or conversations about school. At the next stages, the opportunity is created to draw up a story plan together with the children, independently select micro-topics and freely discuss their content [6; p. 44]. Oral creativity is formed in children on the basis of perceiving examples of literary and folk oral works, including proverbs, riddles, phraseological units in harmony with content and artistic form. The theme of creative stories should serve to educate children in the right attitude towards the surrounding life, respect for adults, love for younger ones, friendship and loyalty. It is important that the topics are close to the life experience of children, understandable and interesting for them. Only then will children become interested in weaving a fairy tale or story. In order to develop creative abilities, children are recommended to be given tasks to come up with a continuation of the author's text. For example, after reading the story “What the Bear Dreamed” by the Uzbek writer Anvar Obidjon, the educator can ask the children to continue it. The educator first shows an example and explains how to imagine the ending of a fairy tale or story. Children's verbal creativity is not limited to fairy tales and stories. They also create poems, riddles, counting rhymes, and small-scale folklore examples. Short rhymed poems are especially popular among children, with the help of which the leader is identified or roles are assigned. Riddles play a special role in the development of children's thinking and speech. Regularly introducing children to folk and literary riddles, analyzing their artistic means, and organizing special vocabulary exercises form the skills of independently composing riddles in children [5; pp. 24–28]. Another important feature of the story is that it can express the characters' character, appearance, location, and the author's reflections. Therefore, in methodological literature, narratives containing elements of

description and reflection are interpreted as combined types of monologues (T. Grizik, O. Ushakova, V. Yashin). Pure narrative forms without description and reflection are rare, since it is these elements that further enrich the story and expand its content.

Of course, the individual approach to the formation of children's reading culture is extremely important in the process of creating a story. The main goal of this approach is to involve children with poorly developed speech in active conversation, expand their vocabulary, and develop their skills in free communication.

1. Also, attention was paid to the pedagogical conditions necessary for describing books read to children in experimental work:

2. Constantly enriching the experience of preschool children with impressions from the world around them. The content of such work has a different nature depending on the specific task: excursions, observing the work of adults, viewing pictures, illustrations in books and magazines, reading books, using media resources.

3. Formation and activation of vocabulary. Children of this age group need to replenish and activate the vocabulary due to new words, phraseological units, words-definitions; words that help describe the experiences of heroes, character traits. Therefore, the process of enriching children's experience is closely related to the formation of new concepts, new vocabulary and the ability to use existing vocabulary.

4. Creative storytelling is the most effective type of activity, the final result of which should be a coherent, logically connected story. A modern child lives under the influence of various technologies, information communications, which limits the child's communication. Therefore, one of the conditions is that children should be able to tell coherently, master the structure of a coherent narrative, know the composition of a narrative and description. Children learn these skills at an earlier age, multiplying literary texts, composing descriptions of toys and pictures, and inventing stories based on them. Especially close to oral creativity are stories about one toy that invented the beginning and end of the episode depicted in the picture.

5. Children can "invent", that is, create something new, talk about something that does not actually exist, or correctly understand the task of "inventing" something that the child himself has not seen.

It was recommended that educators of preschool educational organizations use the following methods of work to increase children's interest in books:

-develop a schedule for instilling in children the concepts of love for the Motherland, respect for parents, friendship, decency and hard work through fairy tales, proverbs, and stories given in books;

- organize conversations and stage performances for each work and teach them to rely on books in case of any problematic situations with suggestions such as "Let's look at our book, what is written in it?";

- organize events with children in preschool educational organizations, dialogues, round tables, competitions such as "Book Festival", "Visit to Book Grandfather", "Meeting with a Storyteller", "My Father, Mother and I Tell a Fairy Tale";

- allow children to weave the final part of the fairy tales themselves;

-to conduct exercises such as finding the hero of the work mentioned among the pictures depicting the heroes of fairy tales and stories or recognizing him by verbal description, finding out which work the sentences mentioned are from, inviting him to draw a picture based on the fairy tale or story he heard; -to include a "New Fairy Tale Hour" in the agenda;

-to draw attention to the fact that among the prizes prepared for the child at various events and competitions organized in the preschool educational organization, there must be a book;

- effective methods and techniques can be used, such as roundtable discussions and practical activities aimed at increasing the child's attitude to books between parents, as well as enriching the knowledge and understanding of parents about books intended for preschool children and their content, and promoting new books created for children.

The educator of preschool educational organizations recommends various works to parents for reading in the family circle in accordance with the age and individual characteristics of the child, shows methods and ways to introduce the child to fiction. Based on the opinions of parents and the content of literature on the subject, we offer methods of working with books in a family setting:

-regularly reading to the child stories, children's poems with repeating phrases, various stories from picture books;

-choosing stories about animals, toys, dinosaurs, circuses, etc. to read to the child;

-use every opportunity to communicate with the child:

talk to the baby, answer his questions about books and surrounding objects;

-allow the child to freely use a pencil, scissors, and paper while listening to a work of art;

-write down the stories the child tells;

-from time to time take the child to a bookstore or a library and give the child, firstly, the opportunity to browse through the books on the shelves or in the reading room; secondly, create the opportunity to choose books and take them with him;

-support your child's interests and be patient. In the development of the reading culture of modern children today, it is necessary to develop and implement special methods for the formation of preschool children's speech, taking into account their specific characteristics and allowing them to fulfill the social order of their parents. The most important task in this is to prepare the child for school education in a high-quality way. It is precisely the formation of a reading culture in children based on an individual approach to education that can be the solution to this problem.

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